
INFLUENCE OF CINEMA ON LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Mr. Mahesh Krishna Mali

Assistant Professor, Department of English,
Bharati Vidyapeeth's Matoshri Bayabai Shripatrao Kadam Kanya Mahavidyalaya,
Kadegaon, Dist. Sangli State- Maharashtra
Corresponding Author - Mr. Mahesh Krishna Mali

Email - 1983malimahesh@gmail.com

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7734311

Abstract:

Cinema is young art which is emerged from photography in the late 19th century in France. It is a machine art which is depending on mechanical equipment for both its creation and exhibition. It uses camera and can record music, drama, painting, operas sculpture and any other arts. Camera plays very important role in making the cinema. The narrative of the films moves with the camera and it acts as an eye of the audience. Cinema reached all over the world through different experiments and become popular. Early cinema was silent and produced in black white color reels only. Later on in 1930 the sound was introduced and also colors. Since inception, cinema has great impact on the lives of individuals and society. A good cinema changes your perception of society and individuals. It changes your attitude towards the world and changes how you see your relationships with other people. It guides us in our life journey and how you see what's possible in future. The most important is it changes how you see yourself. It can help to understand the learning and understanding of other languages. It motivates the viewer to learn language as well as enhances understanding of language. English language in India is a foreign language and many people wish to learn English language because of its international status. Advanced technology of cinema brought new possibilities in learning language. The present paper tries to study the influence of cinema on learning English language.

Introduction:

Cinema is one of the scientific inventions of man through which he could explore new ideas along with changed approaches to human life and its desires, emotions, and feelings. Through the invention of cinema, man could visualize his vision. The visualization has made the art of cinema distinct from other art.

Rather it has helped the audiences and its taste bearers to connect with the story more closely than literature. Cinema displays an imaginative world before the spectator to view, feel, and even think over it. Basically, the spectators view the film through the filmmaker's imagination. Cinemas are very important medium of entertainment as well as communication. It

has great impact on society and individual life because it helps us to understand the society and also connecting to the people of other culture. As films are about and around the people, it reflects the problems of society and makes us familiar with them. It also enhances or gives knowledge of society and make aware about the different issues. Films inspire people to broaden their thinking and imagination.

There are multiple purposes of films and it affects people in different way. Films have motivational or inspirational values can build the confidence of viewer. Films motivate to individuals or society to make career in particular thing in life. Apart from building the confidence, films also responsible for making social change or creating social awareness. Films reflect the values of society based on the culture and history of particular nation. Many documentary films were made about the inventions and discoveries which help to develop scientific temperament among the youth. Some films expand our knowledge of history and culture. Apart from the expanding historical information, films also taught some cultural values. Entertainment is one of the important purposes of films. Some films have educational values and spread the importance of education in the transformation of people's lives. Song and music creates or changes mood of people.

Apart from the above purposes films can be used for educating the masses or students. Education is the backbone on any nation and the future of nation depends on the good education of children's and youths. Being a popular medium of mass communication, films are used in educational filed for the purpose of teaching learning. Students can easily understand the content and subject through films. Films can encourage and motivate the students for learning and acquiring knowledge of the particular field.

British people have introduced English language to Indian people. English is a foreign language in India; so many people have difficulties in learning English language. Students and teachers of English literature do not have much knowledge of the English culture which is reflected in English language as well as in literature. While learning English literature teacher has to compare and contrast the foreign culture with our own culture. The purpose of teaching English literature in Indian classroom is to improve the English language as an international language and also introduce the culture of other nation. Teacher has to use different techniques of teaching English language.

Films are considered as one of the audio-visual aids which may be described as aids that facilitate the understanding of the written and spoken word in a teaching

learning situation. They appeal to the senses such as eyes and ears which are sources of learning. What we learn through senses remain in our mind for longer time. The effectiveness of learning through senses or through audio-visual aids is more effective. These audio-visual aids are of great value in the learning and teaching of English language and literature in India.

Considering the motivation values of film, the researcher has selected the film *English Vinglish* (2012) directed by Gauri Shinde as a case study. Gauri Shinde is Indian film director and the story of the film *English Vinglish* is inspired from the director's own personal life. The director's mother is a Marathi speaking woman who runs a pickle business at her house in Pune. Her mother is not a fluent speaker of English which embarrasses the director as a child. The director Gauri Shinde decided to make a film on the said theme focusing importance of learning English language in changing new world. Sridevi, the Bollywood actress played the major role in the film and wins the appraisal of many people. The film *English Vinglish* (2012) was nominated and wins different awards. The film wins 11 awards and there were 35 nominations. The film received worldwide popularity; the IMDB has given 7.8 ratings out of 10 for this film. The film becomes famous because of the performance of actors and direction.

Mr. Mahesh Krishna Mali

In the film Shashi Godbole (Sridevi) is an Indian housewife who has a small business enterprise of making and selling *laddus*. Her husband Satish and daughter Sapana mocks her because she does not speak good English. They treat her with disrespect and take her granted as ordinary woman doing nothing. She feels insecure and negative feelings. However, her young son and mother-in-law supports her and tries to make her comfort.

While visiting New York City for wedding of her sister's daughter, one fellow passenger from plain motivated and gave inspirational advice to her. She has very sad experience at a cafe where the waitress behaved with her rudely because of her inability to communicate in English. After that incident, she strongly decided to learn English. She joined Conversational English Speaking class of four week. She became promising and confident student. Because of her ability to learn, strong desire and enthusiastic nature, she earns everyone's respect with her charming behavior. Her confidence is increased and she also started to speak in English.

She takes lot of efforts to learn English. She starts watching English films at night and does her homework regularly. She has to give five minutes speech test to get certificate. During the time of test her husband and family members join the wedding at New York earlier than planned.

She is confused because she was learning English secretly. She tries to continue attending the class but decided to quit the class and test because of her busy schedule and confusion. She missed the spoken English test because of the wedding ceremony on that same day.

Shashi's classmates attended the wedding in which she introduced her family in English which is surprising thing for everyone especially her husband Satish. She was considered as a typical Indian housewife but now there is drastic change in her speaking. Her speech emphasizes the virtue being married and having a family describing family as safe place of love and respect. She expects from family members that weakness should not be mocked. The class coordinator declared that she has passed the course and issues her certificate.

This film *English Vinglish* is a motivational story of typical housewife. The film became very popular and inspired many people including young-old, men-woman. It shows that motivation is the first step through which we can make progress. After watching the film everyone get inspired to learn and speak English. This film has great value in motivating the people to learn English.

English films have also great help in acquiring speaking skill of English language. Language can be learned easily

by creating surrounding or atmosphere. In Indian context, very few families speak English at home, so new learners of English do not get proper environment to learn. One can create such surrounding by watching films. Hollywood films have great impact on learning English language worldwide. Hollywood is American film industry particularly in English language. It rules on the heart of millions of movie lover worldwide. Hollywood has a very wide reach cater to the Global audience. Hollywood films have its own standard and have clearly marked feature and their films are of high qualities. Hundreds of movies began made each year and Hollywood alone was considered a cultural icon. Thus Hollywood movies can play vital role in improving English learning and speaking.

Another way of improving English language is through subtitles of films. Subtitles are translation of audio into a different language. They are lines of dialogues or other text displayed at the bottom of the screen in films. Sometimes it is used in television programs or other visual media. They can be transcriptions of the screenplay, translations of dialogues or information to help the audience who are unable to hear or understand what is shown. It can also help the people who can hear the audio but may not be able to understand the conversation. Subtitles can

be rendered as a part of the video or separately as graphics or text overlaid in the video. People can improve the reading skill as well as understanding of English language through subtitles.

Videos prepared for English speaking are also useful for learning and speaking English. Some scholars prepare video content regarding English speaking and upload on electronic platforms such as YouTube. There are lot of videos or short films about English language and literature. They help us to understand and enhance knowledge about English language and literature. These films or videos are very useful and important source of developing different skills of English language.

Conclusion:

Thus, cinema is powerful tools of entertainment as well as education. It affects everyone powerfully because the combined impact of images, music, dialogues, lightening, sound and special effects. The films have capacity to change the mind of individual or society. It has educational impact on the life of students. Any person can start to learn speaking English motivated from films. The different techniques used in films such as subtitles which enhance reading and

comprehension ability of the person. Different videos on YouTube also help in learning and developing English language. Thus, cinemas have great influence in learning English language.

References:

1. Bluestone, George. *Novels into Films: The Metamorphosis of Fiction into Cinema*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1973
2. Hayward, Susan. *Key Concepts in Cinema Studies*. London & NY: Routledge, 2004
3. Hayward, Susan. *Key Concepts in Cinema Studies*. London: Routledge, 2004.
4. Hutcheon, Linda. *A Theory of Adaptation*. New York: Routledge. 2006.
5. Monaco James, *How to Read Films: The World of Movies Media and Multimedia*. New York, 2000.

Films

1. *English Vinglish*. Dir. Gauri Shinde. Eros Worldwide,.2012 Film

Websites

1. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/filmtheory>
2. <http://www.imdb.com>
3. <http://www.wikipedia.com>.